

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Lessons learned from existing carbon removal methodologies for agricultural soils to drive European Union policies

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Abstract

Soil plays a central role in the global carbon (C) cycle and the fight against climate change as it contains the largest existing organic C stock on earth. Natural processes exacerbated by climate change and unsustainable agricultural soil management practices are contributing to the steady decrease in organic C stocks in farmland. Carbon farming practices, underpinned by various incentives, can be used to maintain and increase C stocks in agricultural soils. Carbon credit mechanisms, that is, tradable credits each corresponding to one tonne of CO₂eq, are one such incentive. Carbon credits are issued upon the demonstration of increased soil C stocks over time through the application of C accounting methodologies for each agroecosystem and farming practice. This study presents a detailed and critical analysis of carbon credit methodologies, focusing on agricultural soil C in temperate zones, by comparing the European Commission proposal for a regulation on carbon removals with relevant certification frameworks implemented in extra-European Union industrialized countries (Australia, Alberta in Canada, United States). Based on this, we recommend strengthening the European Commission proposal by (i) expanding the list of eligible agricultural practices, (ii) setting a minimum maintenance time frame for each agricultural practice and incentivizing longer duration, (iii) setting the Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions of the European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) as a regulatory baseline, (iv) beyond the regulatory baseline, defining a farm level baseline in terms of carbon farming practices applied that can be monitored through the Integrated Administration and Control System of the CAP, (v) clarifying the interaction between the European Commission proposal of regulation and the CAP, the Soil Monitoring Law, and Land Use/Cover Area Frame Survey inventory, (vi) retaining a portion of unsold carbon credits as a buffer against the risk of reversal and (vii) applying a default discount to account for leakage risk if yield

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reductions are observed. We propose these recommendations to guarantee effective environmental protection, technical and bureaucratic feasibility as well as economic affordability for farmers.

KEYWORDS

carbon credits, carbon farming, certification, regulatory compliance market, soil carbon accounting, voluntary carbon market

1 | INTRODUCTION

Soils contain the largest terrestrial organic carbon (C) pool (1500–2400 PgC), around three times the size of the pool in the atmosphere (589 PgC) or vegetation (450–650 PgC) (IPCC, 2014). Soil organic carbon (SOC) is the C pool contained in all dead organic matter in soil (Don et al., 2024). Mitigating climate change requires that the soil carbon pool is maintained and possibly increased. Estimates indicate that an annual increase of 0.4% of global SOC stocks would potentially compensate for the observed increase of CO₂ in the atmosphere (Rumpel et al., 2020).

Croplands in the European Union (EU), however, are estimated to lose about 7.4 million tC y⁻¹ via soil degradation and inappropriate soil management (EC, 2021a). Additionally, the extent of wetlands and peatlands is decreasing due to artificial drainage, causing the highest proportion of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from the Agriculture and Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry sector in Central and Northern European countries, such as Germany (Tiemeyer et al., 2020). These SOC losses from agricultural soils are exacerbated by climate change across all climatic zones (Poeplau & Dechow, 2022).

Changes in SOC stocks are the result of C inputs through plant biomass or organic amendments, on one hand, and C losses through microbial decomposition (respiration) (Bondeau et al., 2007) and erosion (Chenu et al., 2019), on the other hand. Under constant climatic conditions and management, SOC content will reach an equilibrium where carbon inputs equal carbon losses. For this reason, increasing SOC stocks require management changes by farmers (Paul et al., 2023), that is, the application of sustainable agricultural practices (Smith et al., 2016), specifically targeted to sequester carbon (*Carbon Farming*, CF). CF practices can influence SOC stocks by either increasing C inputs into soil or decreasing SOC losses (Chenu et al., 2019). The removal of C from the atmosphere and its storage in the soil via carbon sequestration is referred to as carbon removals (CRs). However, many soils lose carbon, and agricultural measures aimed at building up soil C may only lead to C loss mitigation (Don et al., 2024).

Highlights

- The European Commission must define a carbon removals accounting methodology for agricultural soil
- Upon extra-European Union certification schemes, scientific and policy analysis, recommendations are proposed
- Interoperation with Common Agricultural Policy and Soil Monitoring Law systems and Land Use/Cover Area Frame Survey inventory is suggested
- We suggest Common Agricultural Policy conditionality as regulatory baseline and to verify additionality at farm level

The European Commission (EC) listed the most effective CF practices in the ‘Communication on sustainable carbon cycles’ (EC, 2021b):

- i. afforestation and reforestation;
- ii. agroforestry;
- iii. use of catch crops and cover crops;
- iv. conservation tillage;
- v. landscape features;
- vi. conversion of croplands to fallow or of set-aside areas to permanent grasslands;
- vii. restoration of peatlands and wetlands.

The work of the agricultural sector to reduce GHG emissions and increase C stocks is part of the wider effort of the EU to become climate neutral by 2050, as established in the European Climate Law (European Parliament & Council, 2021a). Moreover, a specific target has been set for CRs in the Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry sector (−310 Mt CO₂ eq) by 2030, in the Regulation (EU) n. 2023/839 (European Parliament & Council, 2023)). This strategy aligns with the forecasts of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) which highlight that only if CRs are included in the scenarios, can global warming be limited to 1.5°C, relative to pre-industrial

times (IPCC, 2018). Hence, the EC has proposed a regulation to establish an EU certification framework for carbon removals (CRCF) to compensate for unavoidable or hard-to-abate emissions (EC, 2022) through:

- i. permanent carbon storage (e.g. bioenergy with carbon capture and storage and direct air carbon capture and storage),
- ii. CF and
- iii. carbon storage in products (carbon stored in long-lasting products or materials, such as furniture made of wood).

The variation in SOC stocks over time will be assessed through accounting methodologies described in the CRCF and verified by authorized certification bodies resulting in the creation of CR certificates and credits. These credits can then be purchased on the voluntary carbon market, established and regulated at the European level, by those that *want* to offset their emissions in the sectors listed in the Effort Sharing Regulation (road transport, buildings, agriculture, waste and small industries).

This voluntary carbon market is separate from the European-regulated carbon market, also known as the Emissions Trading System, that sets emission reduction targets in energy-intensive sectors (energy generation, manufacturing industry, aviation) and the number of credits that can be exchanged between Emissions Trading System sectors to compensate for hard-to-abate emissions. Regulated carbon markets also exist in extra-EU countries, such as California (U.S.), Alberta (Canada) and Australia. They are the outcomes of international agreements such as the Climate Change Convention of the United Nations (UNFCCC), the Kyoto Protocol and successors. In non-EU contexts, CF credits can also access the regulated carbon market where credits can be purchased by subjects that *must* offset their emissions. For instance, in California, removals quantification, monitoring, verification and reporting (MRV) methodologies developed by private entities to account for CRs in agriculture have been approved to serve for the California cap-and-trade market (ACR, 2019; CAR, 2020; Government of California, 2018). In Australia, methodologies are defined directly by governmental bodies (Australian Government, 2020; Clean Energy Regulator of the Australian Government, 2021; Minister for Industry Energy and Emissions Reduction of the Australian Government, 2021).

This provides evidence of the role that agriculture plays in different countries to offset emissions from other sectors. Nevertheless, the voluntary carbon market is facing two fundamental problems in addressing climate change mitigation (Boyd et al., 2023):

- i. At least 90% of the offsets traded in the voluntary market have been issued upon avoided emissions (e.g. avoided deforestation); therefore, they do not correspond to a reduction in atmospheric carbon dioxide amounts;
- ii. CR estimates based on different methodologies are not comparable for their accuracy as well as for the guaranteed timescale of the carbon storage, and therefore differ in their effectiveness in mitigating climate change despite being traded on the same market at the same price.

The CRCF is working towards solving these two problems by only issuing credits based on CRs and by proposing a single MRV methodology. The need for a single methodology is also motivated by the fact that, to date, at least 156 different CR certification schemes have been developed in Europe in the absence of common rules (see: <http://reports.crea.gov.it/powerbi/CarbonSchemesInventory.html>).

The CRCF is under review by the European Parliament and the Council (spring–summer 2024) and is still very vague. Further refinement of the methodology is expected in the following months through delegated and executive acts.

This article will compare extra-EU examples of CF removal MRV methodologies and certification frameworks with the CRCF. The analysis focuses on key aspects such as the selection of CF practices, SOC change estimates (definition of baseline and additionality, SOC accounting method) and risks (permanence, reversal and leakage). An evaluation of the CRCF approach will be provided, based on scientific evidence, and existing gaps will be highlighted. We will describe how relevant extra-EU schemes deal with the same issues and propose lessons to be learnt from these initiatives. We also propose an analysis of relevant EU governance and administrative structures to promote interoperability and achieve cheaper and more efficient MRV systems. Based on this analysis, we make recommendations to strengthen the CRCF and to define the delegated acts to come by guaranteeing effective environmental protection, technical and bureaucratic feasibility, as well as economic affordability for farmers.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Analytical approach: System boundaries

We selected seven extra-EU carbon credit initiatives (Table 1), which have a methodology dedicated to the estimation of carbon stocks in agricultural soils and their

TABLE 1 Extra-European Union and European Commission soil carbon removals methodologies considered in the present article; abbreviations; description of their status of implementation; websites and documental sources.

Country	Region	Organization/program (abbreviations)	Methodology (abbreviations)	Status	Website	Documental sources
U.S.A.		American Carbon Registry (ACR)	Avoided conversion of grasslands and shrublands to crop production 2.0 (ACGS)	Active	https://americancarbonregistry.org/	ACR, 2019
U.S.A.		Climate Action Reserve (CAR)	Avoided grassland conversion protocol 2.1 (AGC)	Active	https://www.climateactionreserve.org/	CAR, 2020
U.S.A.		Climate Action Reserve (CAR)	Soil Enrichment Protocol v 1.1 (SEP)	Active	https://www.climateactionreserve.org/	CAR, 2022
U.S.A.		Verra—Verified Carbon Standard Program (Verra)	VM0042 Methodology for Improved Agricultural Land Management v 1.0 (VM0042)	Approved but under revision	https://verra.org/	VCS, 2020
U.S.A.		Nori	Nori Croplands Methodology, v 1.3 (NCM)	Active	https://nori.com/	Nori, 2021
Canada	Alberta	Standard for Greenhouse Gas Emission Offset Project Developers Technology, Innovation and Emissions Reductions Regulation, Alberta government (Alberta Government)	Quantification Protocol for Conservation Cropping Version: 1.0 (QPCC)	Withdrawn on December 31, 2021	https://open.alberta.ca/publications/9780778596288	Government of Alberta, 2012
Australia		Emissions Reduction Fund established by the Carbon Credits—Carbon Farming Initiative—Act of the Australian Government (Australian Government)	Supplement to the Carbon Credits—Carbon Farming Initiative—Estimation of Soil Organic Carbon Sequestration using Measurement and Models—Methodology Determination 2021 (CCM)	Active	https://www.legislation.gov.au/Details/F2021L01696	Minister for Industry Energy and Emissions Reduction of the Australian Government, 2021 Clean Energy Regulator of the Australian Government, 2021
Europe	European Union (EU)	European Commission (EC)	Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Establishing a Union Certification Framework for Carbon Removals—COM(2022) 672 final (CRCF)	Proposal	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52022PC0672	EC, 2022

variation due to the application of CF practices. The high number of private and public schemes existing and emerging (Paul et al., 2023) would make compiling a comprehensive review of soil carbon credits exceptionally challenging. Thus, we focused on methodologies developed in temperate zones of industrialized countries that were applied to farming systems with mineral soils (peatlands are excluded from this analysis) as these soils cover much of European cropland and grassland surface (Bey et al., 2021). This allowed for comparison with the EU context. We specifically selected methodologies developed in North America and Australia, where there are well established pre-existing soil carbon markets compared with other regions (Baumber et al., 2020; Cevallos et al., 2019; Marks, 2020; McDonald et al., 2021). The selected methodologies included:

- the two main offset project producers for agricultural soil carbon currently operating in the voluntary market in the U.S.A (Nori and Indigo, that contributed to the definition of the VM0042 Verra methodology presented in this paper) (Barbato & Strong, 2023),
- the oldest private voluntary offset program in the world (American Carbon Registry [ACR], in the U.S.A.),
- the Climate Action Reserve (CAR) from U.S.A., as it dedicated two methodologies to SOC removals, both in croplands and grasslands,
- the Australian Government's CF Initiative which Macintosh (2013) defined as one of the most robust and innovative at global level,
- the Quantification Protocol For Conservation Cropping Version: 1.0 (QPCC) established by the Alberta Government, in Canada, because it was the first Province to start a carbon trading system in North America in 2007 and it was highly impactful (650,000 tC y⁻¹ on a surface of 1/3 of all seeded acres in Alberta) (Alberta Carbon Registries, 2021; Van Wyngaarden, 2022).

Five of these methodologies are in use today, while VM0042 is under revision and the QPCC was withdrawn in December 2021 (Table 1).

2.2 | Analytical framework and literature review

The analysis focused on the aspects addressed in all methodologies listed in Table 1 to guarantee that CRs are an effective instrument for climate change mitigation (Bey et al., 2021; Oldfield et al., 2021; Paul et al., 2023). These aspects are also considered in the CRCF (EC, 2022). In the present article, we analyse the seven main aspects of these methodologies, directly related to the CF implementation and CR estimates:

- Eligible agricultural practices to be applied by land managers for initiating a CR project.
- CRs estimates:
 - Baseline: reference scenario under which the CRs activity was not applied and the corresponding SOC stocks and GHG emissions.
 - Additionality: a concept that can refer to:
 - the CRs, that would not have occurred in the absence of the project activities, that is, in the baseline scenarios,
 - the agricultural management activity, that goes beyond the obligations required by law—regulatory additionality—or would not have taken place if not incentivized by the carbon credit mechanism—financial additionality.
 - Soil carbon accounting method used for the estimate of carbon stocks prior to the CRs activity (t₀) and after a pre-defined amount of time (t₁):
 - Soil sampling at the farm scale.
 - Default values (e.g. SOC stocks at t₀ retrieved from SOC maps or other regionalized information tools; SOC stocks at t₁ and GHG emissions estimated through emission factors for each applied measure and possibly pedoclimatic zone).
 - Remote sensing.
 - Modelling (with SOC at t₀ being estimated by soil sampling or default values).
 - Permanence: for how long CRs are guaranteed to be stocked in the soil.
 - Risk of reversal: the risk that the carbon that is captured and stored through a CRs activity is released back into the atmosphere.
 - Risk of leakage: the risk that higher GHG emissions or SOC losses occur in areas outside the CRs project area, because of the project itself.

The analysis proceeded in two steps:

1. Matrix development: A matrix was created to summarize information for each aspect listed above in a consistent way to facilitate comparison among CRs methodologies and evaluation.
2. Matrix completion: The matrix was completed based on desk research. Information on how each aspect is accounted for in the extra-EU methodologies and in the CRCF was retrieved online from the organization/program websites, official documentation set out by the methodology developers and the EC (see Table 1 for references), academic and grey literature.

The review of the methodologies highlighted the diversity of the approaches applied. Given the complexity of the

topic, it is appropriate to analyse each aspect presented above in sub-sections in the Section 3.

3 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 | Eligible agricultural practices

The CRCF does not specify yet, in the binding part of the regulation, the agricultural practices eligible for CF projects. However, in the recitals section, that is the introductory part of the regulation, it is stated that the ‘*Regulation should take into account farming practices as referenced in the Communication on Sustainable Carbon Cycles*’ which can be summarized as:

- afforestation,
- agroforestry,
- use of catch crops and cover crops,
- conservation tillage,
- increasing landscape features,
- conversion of cropland to fallow or of set-aside to grassland,
- restoration of peatlands and wetlands (Table 2).

The list of practices proposed by the EC is in line with the ones commonly identified in scientific literature and sectorial reports (Bey et al., 2021; Paul et al., 2023).

Afforestation will not be analysed here as the research focuses on the practices that guarantee the arable use of the land.

Agroforestry is a management system that integrates woody species in agricultural land used for crops or livestock. This land use change practice has been defined as one of the most promising to build up SOC stocks both in the top and in the subsoil of croplands in temperate zones thanks to increased C inputs derived by pruning residues, litterfall, root turnover and rhizodeposition (Drexler et al., 2021; Mayer et al., 2022). Nevertheless, agroforestry is proposed as an eligible CF practice only in one of the seven extra-EU methodologies analysed in the present work (Verra, Table 2). This might be because agroforestry is still poorly adopted in western countries (1.5% of U.S. farms, Smith et al., 2022) and to the high initial investment costs that farmers face, for example, for planting perennial crops (Wreford et al., 2017).

The use of cover crops (i.e. avoiding bare soils between harvest and next sowing) is an effective CF practice that allows increased photosynthetic CO₂ absorption through prolonged crop cultivation and reduces SOC losses due to erosion (Plastina et al., 2024; Poeplau et al., 2024). On average, based on a meta-analysis, Qin et al. (2023) reports an increase of 0.21 t C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ for temperate zones. Exceptional results have been observed in Mediterranean woody systems: up to 5.3 t C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ in olive groves, vineyards and almond orchards (Farooqi et al., 2018; Vicente-Vicente et al., 2016), while much lower increases were estimated, by modelling, in Germany (0.06 t C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) and in Swiss croplands (0.05 t C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) (Keel et al., 2023; Seitz et al., 2023). Four of the five extra-EU methodologies analysed here, that deal with cropland management (CAR, Verra, Nori

TABLE 2 Eligible agricultural practices in the soils carbon removals methodologies analysed in the present article.

Organization	Methodology	Eligible agricultural practices
ACR	AGCS	Avoided conversion of grasslands and shrublands to croplands
CAR	AGC	Avoided conversion of grasslands to croplands
	SEP	Fertilization, amendments, irrigation, tillage, residues management, crop rotation, cover crop, fossil fuel, grazing
Verra	VM0042	Fertilization, amendment, irrigation, tillage, residues management, crop rotation, cover crop, agroforestry, grazing
Nori	NCM	Fertilization, amendments, irrigation, tillage, residues management, crop rotation and crop intensity, cover crops, perennials
Alberta Government	QPCC	No-till + shifting from fallow to continuous cropping if managed with no-till
Australian Government	CCM	Fertilization, amendments, irrigation, clay spreading, liming, catch crops, cover crops, re-establishing grazing, etc.
EC	CRCF	‘ <i>Should take into account farming practices as referenced in the Communication on Sustainable Carbon Cycles</i> ’: afforestation, agroforestry, use of catch crops and cover crops, conservative soil management, increasing landscape features, conversion of cropland to fallow or of set-aside to grassland, restoration of peatland

Abbreviations: ACR, American Carbon Registry; AGC, Avoided grassland conversion; CAR, Climate Action Reserve; CRCF, certification framework for carbon removals; EC, European Commission; NCM, Nori Croplands Methodology; QPCC, Quantification Protocol for Conservation Cropping; SEP, Soil Enrichment Protocol.

and the Australian Government), consider cover crops as an eligible CF practice (Table 2).

By contrast, conservation tillage, and especially no-till, is a much-debated practice. Many scientists describe its effectiveness in increasing SOC stocks and reducing GHG emissions (Plastina et al., 2024; Singh et al., 2024). However, Chenu et al. (2019) listed a series of recent global meta-analyses and reviews showing that the effect of no-till is low or non-significant if the whole soil profile (≥ 30 cm) is considered. More significant beneficial effects are observed in Mediterranean regions (Blanco-Moure et al., 2013) and when no-till is used in combination with cover crops, especially legumes (Boddey et al., 2010; Martins et al., 2012; <https://www.fao.org/conservation-agriculture/en/>). Despite this debate, four methodologies out of five (CAR, Verra, Nori and the Australian Government, Table 2) include improved tillage practices among the eligible ones for carbon credits, and the QPCC of the Alberta Government was fully dedicated to the implementation of no-till.

Increasing landscape features such as herbaceous strips and hedgerows on field borders (Mayer et al., 2022) or trees (Beillouin et al., 2023) can be beneficial to SOC while also reducing erosion and nutrient leaching to rivers and increasing biodiversity. However, no extra-EU methodology so far has included it among the eligible CF practices beneficial for SOC (Table 2), and the innovative approach of the EC is notable in this perspective.

Conversion of croplands to fallow can increase SOC by up to 46.5% in the short term (Kozak & Pudelko, 2021), a benefit that is maintained also in the long term when the fallow gradually converts into grassland (Kazlauskaite-Jadzevice et al., 2019) resulting in up to 71.2% more SOC compared with croplands (Kozak & Pudelko, 2021). Overall, the conversion of arable land to grassland was shown to be the most effective practice among six, based on the analysis of modelled scenarios in Europe (Lugato et al., 2014). Conversely, in a recent meta-analysis, Tang et al. (2019) showed that converting grasslands into croplands can cause a SOC loss of 32% in the 0–30 cm layer and 18% in the 30–60-cm soil layer. The importance of maintaining grasslands to soil CRs is illustrated by the fact that two of the seven selected methodologies are specifically about this measure (Table 2). However, we cannot omit that grasslands are mainly used for grazing or fodder production, and the associated livestock GHG emissions are usually much higher than the SOC increase (Wang et al., 2023); therefore, this aspect should be included in the CRs calculation.

Restoration of peatlands will not be discussed here because this work focuses only on cropland and grassland management in mineral soils.

Extra-EU methodologies presented in this work consider also CF practices that are not included in the CRCF:

- crop rotations,
- use of perennials,
- residues management,
- application of organic fertilizers and amendments,
- irrigation management,
- clay spreading,
- liming,
- sustainable grazing techniques.

The impact of crop rotations (planting different crops sequentially on the same plot of land) on SOC is a complex matter considering that it depends on the crops used in the rotation and on the soil management techniques (Skinulienė et al., 2024) as well as climate and soil characteristics (Liu et al., 2022). However, a global-scale meta-analysis summarized results from 167 studies concluding that crop rotations increased SOC by 6.6% compared with continuous crop monoculture (Liu et al., 2022). Possible co-benefits of this practice are increased soil health, yield and farmer's income (Yang et al., 2024). Diversified crop rotation is one of the most agreed upon CF practices among science, policy and practice (agricultural industry and farmers) (Strauss et al., 2023). One example of diversified crop rotation is the use of perennials. Perennials are plants that persist for several years, such as alfalfa or miscanthus, that have been shown to deliver higher carbon inputs than annual crops because of the longer vegetation period and the continuous soil cover (Poeplau & Don, 2014). Four of the five extra-EU methodologies dedicated to cropland management include crop rotation (Table 2).

The input of organic carbon to the soil is considered a more effective measure compared with the avoided C losses achieved by conservation tillage (Chenu et al., 2019). Organic C inputs can be in the form of crop residues or organic fertilizers and amendments (slurry, manure, compost, digestate, biochar) (Beillouin et al., 2023).

Residues management refers to avoiding the use of fire to eliminate agricultural residues and then leaving them on the soil surface or incorporating them into the soil. A recent study by Haas et al. (2022) based on biogeochemical modelling, estimated that if 100% of agricultural residues were returned to the soil, C sequestration rates will reach $0.6\text{ t CO}_2\text{e ha}^{-1}\text{ y}^{-1}$, corresponding to a SOC sequestration potential of 14–30 t $\text{CO}_2\text{e ha}^{-1}$ in EU-27 croplands, even though this climate mitigation benefit is partly compensated by N_2O emissions increase (+17%–30%). However, specifications are needed when agricultural residues are woody. In fact, the input of woody residues to the soil without pre-processing could increase the C/N ratio

causing the immobilization of available N into the microbial biomass, reducing N availability for plants. Consequently, N fertilization would be required, with the associated risk of N leaching and higher soil N₂O emissions (Lugato et al., 2018). Moreover, woody residues might make agronomic works more difficult and increase phytosanitary risks. Another problem could be the competitive uses of agricultural residues: animal feed and bedding, surface mulching in horticulture, industrial uses and the production of energy from renewable sources (Scarlat et al., 2010). The EC does not propose agricultural residues management among the CF practices, while three out of the five extra-EU methodologies dedicated to croplands do so.

Four methodologies dedicated to cropland management (CAR, Verra, Nori and the Australian Government) include organic amendments in the list of eligible CF practices. The risk associated with these practices in most cases is that amendments would have been applied to other agricultural fields in the surrounding areas and therefore do not contribute to an overall increase of SOC stocks globally (see Section 3.2.4 about leakage) (Powlson et al., 2008). This issue can be overcome if local availability estimates of organic amendments are made; if organic amendments are underutilized, the leakage problem does not persist and their use should be encouraged.

The impact of irrigation on SOC stocks is still debated. A recent global meta-analysis suggests that overall irrigation has a negative impact on SOC (Yao et al., 2024) while several studies shows that irrigation can increase primary production, and therefore C inputs to the soil, with magnitude depending on volume of irrigation water and local conditions, for example, the increase may be more pronounced in arid and semi-arid regions (Trost et al., 2013; Zhou et al., 2016). According to Qader et al. (2021), Southern Portugal, most of Spain, Southern Italy, South-Eastern Greece and Cyprus fall into the semi-arid category. Although, in these contexts, irrigation might be very efficient in terms of SOC increase, highly efficient and sustainable water management practices should be applied (Karimidastenaei et al., 2022), given the condition of water scarcity and the occurring climate change impacts (FAO, 2020). Four methodologies out of five (CAR, Verra, Nori and the Australian Government) include irrigation as a CF practice.

The practices of clay spreading and liming are proposed only by the Australian government.

Clay spreading refers to the addition of clay to sandy soils with a clay content lower than 5% (Davenport et al., 2015). It can increase SOC content because of higher C inputs, deriving from improved plant growth, C binding to clay surface and occlusion in micro-aggregates

formed by clay (Schapel et al., 2018). Higher plant growth after clay spreading is due to reduced water repellence, improved weed control, reduced soil erosion potential, increased nutrient and water-holding capacity (Davenport et al., 2015). Although expensive, clay spreading is used in Australia where sandy soils represents 86% of cereal cropping area (McKenzie et al., 2002), while soils with a clay content <5% are rare in Europe (mostly concentrated in the Northern countries) (Ballabio et al., 2016). This is well reflected in the lack of scientific literature on the topic in Europe, while much more studies are conducted in the Australian context. For these reasons, we do not consider clay spreading as a relevant CF practice for the European context.

Liming is the application of materials rich in calcium and magnesium to acid soils to increase pH. This improves nutrient efficiency, soil structure and plant productivity leading to reduced GHG emissions from fertilizers production, SOC protection and increased carbon inputs to the soil (Paradelo et al., 2015). However, liming also causes increased SOC losses due to higher organic matter mineralization and higher soil CO₂ emissions due to carbonate dissolution (Aye et al., 2016). According to Fabian et al. (2014), agricultural ploughed soils in Europe have a median pH of 5.8 and grasslands a value of 5.5, with lower values in northern Europe (mainly Fennoscandia) and higher values in southern Europe, where carbonate rich soils are dominant. Based on this analysis, liming could be a useful CF measure if applied especially in Northern Europe; however, overall, the current scientific evidence has been judged not sufficient to predict its effect on SOC stocks under different conditions (Paradelo et al., 2015).

Sustainable grazing techniques are outside the scope of this paper.

The cultivation of deep-rooting crops (e.g. canola and hemp) is another CF practice supported by strong scientific evidence as these crops contribute to C inputs in a greater volume of soil and for longer time compared with other CF practices (Kätterer et al., 2011; Menichetti et al., 2015; Poeplau et al., 2021). However, no extra-EU methodology so far lists this practice among the eligible options.

The effectiveness of CF practices increases when they are used in combination, for example, when no-till is combined with cover crops, especially legumes (Boddey et al., 2010; Martins et al., 2012) and more generally for the agroecosystem, in application of the agroecological principles (Altieri, 2004).

It is important to highlight that most of the CF practices presented in this section are already incentivized by the current Common Agricultural Policy (CAP 2023–2027). Firstly, SOC protection and increase is promoted

by *conditionality*, that is a set of fundamental obligations of environmental protection that farmers must fulfil if they want to access any form of support from the CAP. These environmental protection standards are named Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC, Reg. EU 2021/2115, Annex III, European Parliament & Council, 2021b) and are listed in Table 3. Beyond these basic environmental standards, the CAP offers a set of extra incentives for those farmers who, on a voluntary basis, decide to contribute more to soil conservation by adhering to further commitments for SOC protection and increase, that is, eco-schemes and agri-environment-climate commitments (Table 3). It is interesting that these measures aim at minimizing possible trade-offs through defined actions. As an example, agri-environment-climate

commitment 13 outlines the application techniques for organic amendments to minimize the associated emissions of pollutants and GHGs, for example, by the application of precision agriculture, direct injection of the organic amendments or its burial right after spreading, etc. (Italy CAP Strategic Plan, 2022). As pointed out by Paul et al. (2023), the CRCF does not yet clarify whether farmers could apply for carbon credits if they received CAP payments for the same measures (the so-called ‘double funding’).

On 5 July 2023, the EC set out a proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (EC, 2023) to promote accurate soil monitoring and sustainable management to achieve healthy soils all over Europe by 2050. The monitoring of soil quality applies also to SOC. The commission presents the principles that

TABLE 3 Measures supported by the Common Agricultural Policy for soil organic carbon protection and increase (REG. European Union 2021/2115, Annex III, European Parliament & Council, 2021b).

Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC)	Eco-schemes	Agri-environment-climate commitments (AECC)
GAEC 1: Maintenance of permanent grassland ratio on national level	Eco-scheme 2: Interrow green covers of tree crops	AECC 3: Minimum tillage
GAEC 2: Adequate protection of wetlands and peatlands	Eco-scheme 4: Extensive forage systems with rotations	AECC 4: Burial of organic matter
GAEC 3: Ban on burning arable stubble except for plant health reasons	Eco-scheme 5: Specific measures for pollinating organisms	AECC 5: Interrow green cover of tree crops
GAEC 5: Tillage management, reducing the risk of soil erosion from a slope of 10% on arable land		AECC 6: Cover crops
GAEC 6: Minimum soil cover on arable land to avoid bare soil in periods that are most sensitive		AECC 7: Land use change from arable land to permanent grasslands
GAEC 7: Crop rotation in arable land (at least a change of crop once per year, except in case of multiannual crops, grasses and fallow), except for crops growing under water		AECC 8: Pastures management
GAEC 8: Minimum share (at least 4%) of arable land devoted to non-productive areas and landscape features, including land lying fallow		AECC 9: Management of natura 2000 sites
GAEC 9: Ban on the conversion or ploughing of permanent grassland in Natura 2000 sites		AECC 10: Management of ecological infrastructures
		AECC 11: Creation of ecological corridors and belts
		AECC 13: Reductions of emissions from farming (organic amendments)
		AECC 21: Management of crop residues (Action n. 2)
		AECC 24: Precision farming
		AECC 29: Organic farming

define sustainable soil management practices (Annex III of the Directive), some of which align with the proposed CF practices in the CRCF:

- cover crops,
- minimize physical soil disturbance,
- creation and maintenance of adequate landscape features,
- ensure optimized water levels in organic soils,

while others go beyond the CRCF:

- maximize efficiency of irrigation management,
- limit the frequency of operations,
- fertilizations adapted to the plant needs,
- crop rotation and diversity, taking into consideration root systems.

Based on these principles, it is the responsibility of the member states to define the sustainable soil management practices, based on the type and use of soils (Art. 10 of the Directive).

3.2 | CRs estimate

Changes in SOC stocks are small compared with larger existing SOC stocks (Don et al., 2024), the spatial and temporal variability of SOC stocks is high (Goidts et al., 2009) and measurement and modelling have uncertainties. Based on different soil characteristics (e.g. parent material, texture, mineralogy, structure, humidity), soils have different SOC storage potentials (Wiesmeier et al., 2019), the rate of SOC accumulation decreases over time (Paul et al., 2023) and increasing SOC stocks is not possible at all locations (e.g. places with limited access to water) (Chenu et al., 2019). For all these reasons, a reliable quantification is challenging but still needed because carbon credits, issued in the framework of a CF project, correspond to a precise amount of CRs, that is, 1 tCO₂e.

3.2.1 | Baseline

To estimate CRs, a scenario where CF practices are applied is compared to a scenario without them (Bartkowski, 2021). This scenario, called a baseline, refers to the agricultural practices that would have been applied in the absence of the CF project and the associated SOC stocks and GHG emissions. A baseline can be:

- specific for every farm, based on historical information on farm management and SOC measurements on soil samples,

- estimated, based on external sources of information (aerial photographs, satellite images, SOC maps, soil type maps, climate data, etc), usually referred to as the ‘standardized baseline’.

The choice between these two types of baseline will impact the certainty of the baseline scenario description and the robustness of the application of the additionality principle (see Section 3.2.2), on one hand, and the administrative burden and costs for farmers, on the other hand (Bey et al., 2021). It is a challenge for every CR methodology to propose a system that compromises between ‘ensuring objectivity, minimising compliance and other administrative costs’ (recital 7, CRCF) to guarantee effective climate mitigation, buyers’ trust and a wide uptake of CF practices.

In the CRCF, the EC refers primarily to a standardized baseline based on data about environmental, geographical, social, economic and technological aspects and the associated CRs for the applied practices. The main risk of this approach is that it does not guarantee that SOC changes really occur in every farm (see the Section 3.2.2). If these reference data are missing, project developers can refer to a baseline directly assessed on their farms (Art. 4, CRCF, Table 4). This may cause great differences between countries and regions in the baseline quality, although carbon credits are then sold on a unique European market, with common quality requirements. To reduce national arbitrariness, referring to a homogeneous description of soil characteristics in Europe would be preferable. This is the objective of the Land Use/Cover Area Frame Survey (LUCAS) inventory, for which sampling campaigns are repeated every 3–7 years (2009, 2015, 2018 and 2022). This information can complement national soil inventories and be a good basis for a standardized baseline. LUCAS information will also be used in the monitoring system proposed by the Soil Monitoring Law. In fact, in Art. 4, Member States are asked to identify soil districts to organize the monitoring system, based on administrative borders or climate, soil type and land use information, the latter possibly deriving from the LUCAS inventory. However, in the LUCAS system, SOC changes have not been described for 2009 and 2015 because bulk density was not measured; therefore, only changes in concentration (‰) were estimated. Moreover, LUCAS quality, representativeness and resolution have been questioned (Bellassen et al., 2022).

Information on the baseline at the farm level could be retrieved by administrative systems (Smith et al., 2020) such as the Integrated Administrative and Control Systems (IACS) which manage and monitor all CAP interventions in every EU country. These systems rely on comparable data throughout the EU such as meteorological data, maps, statistics, positional information and remotely sensed data

TABLE 4 Baseline and additionality criteria set in the soil carbon removals methodologies analysed in the present article.

Organization	Methodology	Baseline	Additionality
ACR	AGCS	Scenario of conversion to croplands and associated practices Updated every 5 years Identification of the conversion agent or probability	Regulatory surplus test Performance standard test
CAR	AGC	Scenario of conversion to croplands and associated practices Valid for up to 50 years Default emission factors developed through a probabilistic approach	Regulatory surplus test Performance standard test
	SEP	Min. of 3 years of historical management information Use of regional average allowed after quality check by CAR	New practice Regulatory surplus test Performance standard test
Verra	VM0042	Scenario of continuation of pre-project agricultural management practices Min. of 3 years	New or change in practices (at least 5% delta) Regulatory surplus test Performance standard test
Nori	NCM	Prior 10 years of historical agronomic practices and past weather data Historical management data for at least 3 years + proxies taken from databases (such as USDA/NRCS) by Nori Dynamic baseline updated based on new weather data	Must show SOC increment over baseline scenario
Alberta Government	QPCC	Conservative tillage management: Census of Agriculture + carbon seq. default values. Summer fallow reduction: use a historic project baseline based on 3-year records	New practice
Australian Government	CCM	Scenario describing 5-year historical data where the land was used for pasture, cropping or bare fallow + soil sampling (t0)	New practice Regulatory surplus test Identification of no 'common practice' Financial additionality
EC	CRCF	<i>'The standard carbon removal performance of comparable activities in similar social, economic, environmental and technological circumstances and take into account the geographical context. Where duly justified, the baseline may be based on the individual carbon removal performance of that activity'. 'The baseline shall be periodically updated'</i>	Regulatory surplus test Due to the incentive effect of the certification

Abbreviations: ACR, American Carbon Registry; AGC, Avoided grassland conversion; CAR, Climate Action Reserve; CRCF, certification framework for carbon removals; EC, European Commission; NCM, Nori Croplands Methodology; QPCC, Quantification Protocol for Conservation Cropping; SEP, Soil Enrichment Protocol; SOC, Soil organic carbon.

regarding all agricultural land parcels in the EU and associated agricultural activities.

Outside of Europe, methodologies referring to the avoided grassland conversion (ACGS by ACR and AGC by CAR, Table 4), set the baseline as the scenario of grassland conversion. In the case of methodologies referring to soil management in croplands, four out of five

require the use of historical agricultural information (3–10 years) documented at the farm level (Soil Enrichment Protocol [SEP] by CAR, Verra, Nori, Alberta Government, Australian Government) or described in agricultural census and regional databases (SEP by CAR, Nori, Alberta Government). Historical information at the farm level reduces the risk that farmers will stop CF practices

for a short period of time before reintroducing them so that the 'new' CF practice can be considered additional (Barbato & Strong, 2023). In CAR and Alberta Government methodologies, the emissions and C stocks associated with the baseline scenarios are obtained by default values, while the Australian government requires the collection of soil samples (t_0 , Table 4).

3.2.2 | Additionality

The principle of additionality refers to additional conditions (SOC stocks, GHG reduction or CF practices) compared with the baseline scenario. The limits of additionality are usually related to the fact that the baseline scenario is static. In fact, financial additionality is usually evaluated compared with a baseline that does not take into account future changes in prices and consumer demand, while regulatory additionality is evaluated compared with a baseline scenario that does not consider future changes in policies (Mitter et al., 2020). This is the reason why CAR and Nori methodologies, similarly to CRCF, require the baseline to be updated over time (Table 4).

Moreover, when additionality is defined compared with a standardized baseline, and not verified at the single farm level, transaction costs (legal, brokerage and monitoring fees) can be reduced, but there is a high risk for additional projects to be excluded and for non-additional projects to be included (Macintosh, 2013). Even if additionality is one of the principles that guarantee the achievement of climate change mitigation, a study run in the U.S.A. and Australia shows that farmers consider the principle of additionality as unfair because it does not reward farmers who started CF practices before the appearance of the incentives (Barbato & Strong, 2023), the so-called pioneers.

The CRCF requires the CR activity to be additional from both the regulatory and financial perspectives. However, the compliance with this principle does not need to be verified if the standardized baseline is set, while if the baseline is established at the farm level, additionality shall be demonstrated (Art. 5 of the CRCF, Table 4). As suggested by Paul et al. (2023), given that GAECs are applied on around 90% of the EU agricultural area, additional scenarios need to consider that numerous SOC increasing measures are already supported by the CAP.

Similarly to the CRCF, the regulatory surplus test is also required by the ACR, CAR and Verra methodologies (Table 4).

In the case of methodologies dealing with soil management in cropland, additionality refers to the application of a new practice for all methodologies (CAR, Verra, Alberta

and Australian Government) apart from the Nori that requires a demonstration of SOC increment over the baseline scenario (Table 4). The latter approach can be defined as 'result-based' (see Section 3.2.3), and although it is the most robust to guarantee additionality, it is the riskiest for farmers. In fact, they must face all the costs related to the change in practices, especially the high cost of soil analysis, and for adhering to the CF project without any guarantees of being rewarded. This is because results also depend on variables that are beyond the farmers' control, notably the weather conditions and the more frequent occurrence of extreme events because of climate change. This risk may decrease the adoption rate of the CF practices, and therefore, their overall climate change mitigation potential, especially considering that their adoption is voluntary (De Cara, 2023).

3.2.3 | SOC estimate method

SOC changes can be estimated by:

- direct measurement with soil sampling coupled with laboratory analysis,
- models,
- remote or proximal sensors,
- emission factors.

Despite the challenges linked to SOC assessment described at the beginning of the Section 3.2, measurement-based methods are the most robust and reliable in describing variations in SOC stocks as well as the impact of uncontrolled factors (e.g. climate events: droughts or heavy rainfalls). However, this method is costly (Paul et al., 2023) and needs to be repeated at least every 3–5 years (FAO & ITPS, 2020). Soil sampling coupled with laboratory analysis is the most suitable assessment technique for 'result-based' payment systems, where farmers are paid based on the actual SOC increases achieved, in contrast to the 'action-based' systems where farmers are compensated solely for adopting specific CF practices (Raina et al., 2024). Soil sampling is the second most frequently proposed SOC assessment method in the extra-EU methodologies analysed in this paper (four methodologies, of which two propose it as optional, Table 5) but is not proposed in the CRCF. Additional information regarding the sampling scale, frequency, method, minimum number of soil samples and SOC analytical method proposed by the methodologies can be found in the [Supplementary Material](#).

Several models have been developed upon the knowledge of SOC dynamics to infer SOC changes (Chenu et al., 2019). Modelling is cheaper than sampling and

TABLE 5 Soil carbon assessment methods proposed in the soil carbon removals methodologies analysed in the present article (Y = YES, N = NO).

Organization	Methodology	Soil organic carbon assessment method			
		Modelling	Default values	Remote sensing	Soil sampling
ACR	AGCS	Y e.g. DAYCENT	N	N	Y Alternative to modelling
CAR	AGC	N	Y Probabilistic approach	N	N
	SEP	Y + sampling	N	N	Y t0 + t5 + t10... +modelling
Verra	VM0042	Y optional	N	Y optional	Y optional
Nori	NCM	Y Tier-3 DAYCENT	N	N	N
Alberta Government	QPCC	Y Empirical model based on default factor	Y	N	N
Australian Government	CCM	Y optional	N	N	Y mandatory
EC	CRCF	Not mentioned	Mentioned in the recitals	Mentioned in the recitals	Mentioned in the recitals but considered not applicable due to analytical costs

Abbreviations: ACR, American Carbon Registry; AGC, Avoided grassland conversion; CAR, Climate Action Reserve; CRCF, certification framework for carbon removals; EC, European Commission; NCM, Nori Croplands Methodology; QPCC, Quantification Protocol for Conservation Cropping; SEP, Soil Enrichment Protocol.

modelling capabilities are continuously progressing. However, models with different levels of complexity exist (e.g. Century, Roth-C) and model calibration as well as high quality input data (e.g. initial SOC stocks, soil management data, often protected by privacy policies) are needed to obtain reliable outputs. Finally, the impact of uncontrolled factors is not adequately accounted for (Paul et al., 2023) and innovative management practices, such as agroforestry, are not yet simulated in SOC models (Chenu et al., 2019). Six out of the seven extra-EU methodologies analysed in the present article opt for modelling, of which ACR, Verra and the Australian Government propose modelling as an alternative option to soil sampling, but this is not proposed in the EC regulation (Table 5). The most used model in the U.S. CR methodologies described in this article is Daycent, a biogeochemical process model. Based on a mixed model-sampling approach, Mathers et al. (2023) showed that, for 14 combinations of crops and agricultural practices, $\geq 90\%$ of the Daycent model prediction interval covered the measured values and that the calibrated parameters could be used for carbon credits projects. The SEP methodology, by CAR, and VM0042 by Verra require, for the

first time, model calibration, validation and estimates of variance based on rigorous methods described in dedicated guidelines developed in collaboration with scientists (Jackson Hammond et al., 2021; Mathers et al., 2023). These requirements highly increase the model prediction's reliability; however, these activities may be highly complex to cope with for farmers. For this reason, there is a growing number of online tools (e.g. LOOC-C developed by the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organization of Australia) providing free estimates of CRs to farmers prior to the beginning of the CF project, as well as carbon service providers and project developers assisting farmers, against payment.

Combinations between measurement and model-based approaches are possible, as is the case for the SEP 1.1 of CAR and the Methodology of the Australian Government (Table 5) and have been proven to be effective for the estimate of SOC stocks changes (Basso et al., 2011; Dungal et al., 2022).

Remote sensing is a promising technology for cost-effective SOC mapping on vast areas (Angelopoulou et al., 2019); however, precise estimations require the soil to be bare, with a low water content and a uniform SOC

content throughout the plough layer (Castaldi et al., 2019). Among the extra-EU methodologies, remote sensing is proposed only by Verra (Table 5).

Research is still needed to establish a robust use of proximal sensors in the field (Angelopoulou et al., 2020), and a combined approach (machine learning, remote sensing, proximal sensing) has been proposed by the scientific community for the Australian CF framework (Li et al., 2023).

A cheaper alternative is the use of default SOC stock change values, often called emission factors, for specific CF practices, without measurement of soil properties and dynamics at the farm level (Paul et al., 2023). Using default values can simplify CR assessments, reducing transaction costs. However, this approach requires prior scientific knowledge to guarantee a certain level of accuracy and may introduce project-level uncertainty (Bey et al., 2021). The use of default values is proposed by AGC (CAR) and the QPCC by the Alberta Government (Table 5). The emission factors chosen by the Alberta Government are inspired by the IPCC emission factors used by the Canada's government for the GHG reporting. These factors were comparable with the SOC increase rate verified by VandenBygaert et al. On 27 long-term experiments (LTE) across Canada, maintained for periods of up to a century. Six of these LTEs were located in Western Canada (Alberta and Saskatchewan) and focused on no-till and six on fallow. The factors were then discounted by the Alberta government based on the adoption level of the above-mentioned practices as declared in the Census of Agricultural (2006, <https://www150.statcan.gc.ca/n1/ca-ra2006/index-eng.htm>).

The CRCF does not yet include detailed information on how the monitoring of soil carbon stocks and their variation over time must be done. The EC aim is that '*Carbon removals shall be quantified in a relevant, accurate, complete, consistent, comparable and transparent manner*' (Art. 4(4)) to build up a result-based CRs certification framework. However, the CRs assessment methodologies will be established in delegated acts (Art. 8) that will be adopted by the EC in the months following the approval of the final regulation text and therefore are not yet available. In the recital (7) of the regulation, the EC suggests promoting '*the use of available digital technologies, including electronic databases and geographic information systems, remote sensing, artificial intelligence and machine learning, and of electronic maps*' to '*decrease the costs of establishing baselines and of monitoring carbon removal activities*' (Table 5).

The use of databases, electronic maps and geographic information describing SOC stocks and changes at the European level will require more European countries to maintain a representative national soil inventory, or that

the LUCAS survey be better exploited (Bellassen et al., 2022). Moreover, as stated before, the soil monitoring law is establishing a mandatory monitoring system for a set of soil health indicators, including SOC, at the EU level. This monitoring would not be useful only for CF, but also in the framework of the national GHG inventories of the EU, which have an alarming level of inaccuracy, with estimated unreported SOC losses in croplands around 70 Mt CO₂ y⁻¹. Another possibility is that measured SOC data collected in the framework of CF initiatives, such as the Label Bas Carbone in France, are shared (Bellassen et al., 2022). Finally, SOC data could be retrieved from the CAP monitoring system that assesses, through annual performance reports, the progress of EU countries in reaching the objectives of the CAP. In the previous CAP programming period (2014–2022), for organic agriculture and agri-environmental measures, the impact of these CAP measures on soil quality has been determined, on a representative sample of farms funded by the CAP, through soil sampling and analysis at the farm level before (ex-ante) and after (ex-post) the CAP measure was applied (Cagliero et al., 2013). The new CAP 2023–2027 monitoring system is established by the EU Regulation 2021/2116, and the indicators are set by the CAP 'new delivery model' 2023–2027, but methodological details are not yet defined (European Parliament & Council, 2021c).

3.2.4 | Permanence, risk of reversal and leakage

CRs should be permanent to effectively contribute to climate change mitigation; however, CRs in soils are generally reversible, in contrast to emission reductions, and farmers should maintain CF measures indefinitely, which is unrealistic and cannot be guaranteed by a limited-length contract (Paul et al., 2023).

CF measures that entail high initial investment costs (e.g. agroforestry) have a higher likelihood of being maintained, at least for a longer time (Wreford et al., 2017). Beyond this economic aspect, a long-term CF practice maintenance can be required by the SOC removals methodology.

In the CRCF, permanence is mentioned but not yet defined in an exhaustive way. In the Art. 6(1), the CRCF states that '*a carbon removal activity aims at ensuring the long-term storage of carbon*' and that '*For carbon farming [...] the carbon stored by a carbon removal activity shall be considered released to the atmosphere at the end of the monitoring period*', but there is not any reference to the minimum duration of the monitoring period (Table 6), and this vague approach contrasts with the majority of the extra-EU methodologies presented below.

TABLE 6 Permanence, risk of reversal and risk of leakage in the soil carbon removals methodologies analysed in the present article.

Organization	Methodology	Permanence time guaranteed	Reversal	Leakage
ACR	AGCS	5–40 years	Risk assessment via an ACR tool % of credits issued goes to a buffer pool	20% market leakage
CAR	AGC	100 years after credits issuance	Risk assessment % of credits issued goes to a buffer pool	20% leakage effect due to displacement of livestock and crop yields reduction
	SEP	100 years (credits issued ex-ante) If <100 years: credits are 1% of the t CO ₂ e stored/year. Issued ex-post	Risk rating % of credits issued goes to a buffer pool	Accounts for displacement of livestock and decline in crop yields (>5%).
Verra	VM0042	Non-permanence risk calculated by the VCS AFOLU Tool	Risk assessment % of credits issued goes to a buffer pool	Extra manure + productivity decline (>5%) + displacement of livestock (emissions as if steady number)
Nori	NCM	10 years	–	'Verification will establish if SOC stock gains result in losses outside of project boundary'
Alberta Government	QPCC	20 years	Discount factors due to tillage events = 7.5–20% of credits (if <10% of the field area, not considered)	Based on ISO 14064:2, activity shift deemed minimal
Australian Government	CCM	100 years or 25 years with 20% discount on credits issued	Buffer: 5% if 100-year permanence 25% if 25-year permanence	The regulator notifies the project for non-genuine carbon abatement
EC	CRCF	Long-term storage and undefined monitoring period	'Operators [...] shall monitor and mitigate any risk of release of the stored carbon occurring during the monitoring period' + in the recitals it mentions liability mechanisms	'the carbon captured [...] should outweigh the emissions [...] that can be caused by carbon leakage'

Abbreviations: ACR, American Carbon Registry; AGC, Avoided grassland conversion; CAR, Climate Action Reserve; CRCF, certification framework for carbon removals; EC, European Commission; NCM, Nori Croplands Methodology; QPCC, Quantification Protocol for Conservation Cropping; SEP, Soil Enrichment Protocol.

Six of the seven extra-EU methodologies set a precise maintenance time of the CF practice between 5 years (ACR) and 100 years (CAR and the Australian Government, Table 6). Setting a 100-year duration is the most reliable approach to guarantee climate change mitigation, however, such a strong commitment risks impeding the uptake of CR projects (Macintosh, 2013). For this reason, the Australian Government offers the option for land managers to reduce the permanence time to 25 years but with a 20% discount on the emitted credits. Similarly, the CAR SEP sets another form of disincentive for land managers who choose a shorter commitment: credits

emission ex-post, instead of ex-ante and on an annual basis (Table 6).

Even if the practice is maintained over a long time, the risk of SOC reversal is not eliminated. In fact, SOC losses can happen because extra soil management practices are required compared with what was scheduled at the time of the CF project definition, or because of uncontrollable climate events (e.g. droughts, floods, fires) (Oldfield et al., 2021). For these reasons, some certificate providers keep part of the credits as an unsold buffer (Murray et al., 2007), even if recently, buffer values have been defined as arbitrary and often too low

(Paul et al., 2023). Four of the seven extra-EU methodologies (ACR, CAR both methodologies and Verra) account for the reversal risk by estimating the risk (e.g. with VCS AFOLU Tool, Verra) and then assigning a % of the issued credits to a buffer pool. The QPCC of the Alberta Government opted for a default discount to the issued credits depending on the types of projects (from 7.5 up to 20% discount) but only if the soil disturbance event concerned more than 10% of the surface area. The Australian Government applies a default buffer value of 5% if the permanence is set to 100 years and a 25% buffer value if the permanence is set to 25 years. The latter approach stimulates the application of longer-term projects; however, 25 years is already a long-time span for farmers planning; therefore, a 25% buffer seems very high and might impact negatively on the implementation rate of CF projects. The Nori Croplands Methodology 1.3 does not account for reversal risk (Table 6).

Recently, some researchers pointed to the fact that also temporary CRs contribute to climate change mitigation (Leifeld & Keel, 2022), but methodologies to quantify such an effect are not available yet. Moreover, Chenu et al. (2019) pointed out that labile fractions of SOC (e.g. with residence times of months to years) are essential in terms of soil fertility, soil physical conditions and soil biodiversity; therefore, labile SOC increase should not be discouraged. However, these factors are only indirectly linked to the climate change mitigation potential of CF practices, and therefore cannot be included in the SOC removals calculation.

Regarding the risk of reversals, the CRCF at the Art. 6, paragraph 2 (a) states that ‘Operators [...] shall monitor and mitigate any risk of release of the stored carbon occurring during the monitoring period’, and in the recitals, the CRCF refers to several liability mechanisms, such as ‘discounting of carbon removal units, collective buffers or accounts of carbon removal units, and up-front insurance mechanisms...’ but without opting for one of these liability options in the articles section (Table 6).

Another risk that reduces the mitigation capacity of the CF practice is the leakage risk (Searchinger et al., 2008), that is the risk that SOC improvements in one location cause SOC deteriorations or GHG emissions in other locations, outside the project boundaries (Paul & Helming, 2019). For example, the production intensity might be increased in other locations, or land use change from natural environments to cropland might occur to compensate for a reduction in yield in fields where CF practices were applied (Leifeld et al., 2019). As in the case of reversal, reliable models to account for this risk are still lacking especially for small-scale management changes. However, some of the extra-EU methodologies

proposed examples to deal with this aspect. The two methodologies referring to the avoided conversion of grasslands set a default value of 20% discount factor applied to the baseline emissions. VERRA requires that CF projects guarantee a <5% reduction in crop production (Table 6) and accounts for the GHG emissions linked to the application of extra manure in the field, compared with the baseline. Three other methodologies do not propose a quantified approach because the Alberta Government considered this risk as minimal (Oldfield et al., 2021); the Nori methodology states that ‘*Verification will establish if SOC stock gains result in losses outside of project boundary*’, and similarly and the Australian Carbon Credits Methodology states that ‘*The Regulator notifies the project for non-genuine carbon abatement*’ (Table 6).

In the CRCF the EC states, in the recitals section, that ‘*the carbon captured [...] should outweigh the emissions [...] that can be caused by carbon leakage*’. However, this general principle is not mentioned and further developed in the following articles section, the binding part of the regulation (Table 6).

As proposed by the Australian Carbon Credits Methodology, a possible approach to account for non-permanence, reversal and leakage risks is to estimate CRs with an overall conservative approach. This choice will further guarantee the credibility of CR projects but will further reduce their financial profitability and therefore might hamper the realization of CRs full potential of climate change mitigation (Macintosh, 2013).

4 | RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the information reported in the previous sections, we propose the following recommendations to the CRCF.

4.1 | Eligible agricultural practices

We recommend expanding the list of eligible agricultural practices to include:

- diversified crop rotation (e.g. use of legumes in combination with no-tillage, deep-rooting crops, perennials)
- crop residues management leaving residues on the soil surface, but in case of woody residues, it would be preferable to pretreat them (e.g. by composting)
- application of organic amendments and fertilizers through sustainable application techniques, after a local evaluation of leakage risk and plants' nutrient needs

- efficient irrigation techniques in semi-arid regions,

and among the currently considered practices, we propose to promote the application of no-till mainly in Mediterranean environments.

Moreover, to avoid incoherence among policies and to optimize the use of resources, the CRCF should also clarify how it relates to:

- the CAP, to avoid double funding for the same practice,
- the Soil Monitoring Law, in terms of the definition of sustainable management practices affecting SOC.

4.2 | Baseline and additionality

To respect the regulatory additionality principle, we recommend considering the GAECs of the CAP as a regulatory baseline, that can be easily and cheaply monitored through the IACS of the CAP. As a consequence, additionality will at least imply the application of practices that go beyond the GAECs.

However, to guarantee a real change in agricultural management at the farm level, we recommend that a CF practice baseline is set at farm level based on historical data (at least 5 years) about agricultural management and SOC. Similarly, additionality, in terms of CF practices, should be verified at the farm level, compared with the historical management data. To minimize the costs of the baseline and additionality monitoring, we recommend that information on farm management is retrieved from the IACS of the CAP.

If a standardized baseline is chosen, we recommend using data on land use and SOC produced by the LUCAS survey, if national data are not available, and to follow the same soil areas definition chosen by each member state to monitor soil health, including SOC, in the framework of the Soil Monitoring Law.

4.3 | SOC removals estimate method

If the approach of using databases, electronic maps and GIS is confirmed, we recommend:

- using national SOC maps and land use maps,
- if national maps are not available, we recommend:
 - the use of LUCAS inventory
 - to set up interoperability with the upcoming Soil Monitoring Law monitoring system
 - to set up interoperability with the CAP monitoring system.

Upon these data on initial SOC and land use, the estimate of the SOC dynamics could be made by modelling (Bellassen et al., 2022) such as Daycent, when properly calibrated and validated for the specific CF practice and with a defined uncertainty assessment methodology.

If high quality entry data for modelling are not available, emission factors can be used after validation based on results of LTEs in Europe (VandenBygaart et al., 2010).

If soil sampling will be chosen as SOC assessment methodology, we recommend stimulating the aggregation of multiple enterprise-scale CR projects to mitigate the monitoring costs as well as the risks associated with a purely result-based approach.

Finally, we recommend updating the delegated acts of the regulation upon the results of several research projects funded at the EU level to define MRV methodologies for CF that are currently ongoing.

4.4 | Permanence, risk of reversal and leakage

Define a time of maintenance for each eligible CF practice. The minimum time should be 5 years. Longer maintenance time should be incentivized by applying CRs discounts on short projects.

To favour interoperability with the IACS of the CAP, the monitoring time of CRs shall align with the CAP program's period.

The risk of reversal should be accounted for by keeping a fixed portion (%) of the credits as an unsold buffer. The portion of buffer credits should be higher for shorter projects.

To account for the risk of leakage, we recommend that a default discount (%) on issued credits is applied depending on the observed yield reduction compared with regional averages for the same year.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

Mitigating climate change through CF is an uncertain approach due to the difficulties in SOC monitoring and the risks of reversal and leakage. Reducing GHG emissions should be the main aim of the EU policy on climate. Given the necessity to compensate hard-to-abate emissions and keeping in mind that CF practices can bring co-benefits such as climate change adaptation, a wider participation in carbon offsetting projects is to be encouraged. For this, the EC must set up a reliable and feasible CRs accounting methodology in agriculture.

Based on a review of seven extra-EU methodologies for soil carbon accounting in mineral agricultural soils,

scientific evidence and policy analysis, we recommend that the proposed EC regulation on CRs:

- Expands the list of eligible agricultural practices.
- Clarifies the interaction with the CAP and the Soil Monitoring Law.
- Sets the GAECs of the CAP as a regulatory baseline, to be monitored through the already existing IACS of the CAP.
- Beyond the regulatory baseline, it sets a CF practices baseline at the farm level, based on historical agricultural management that can be monitored from the IACS of the CAP.
- If a standardized baseline is chosen, we recommend using data on land use and SOC produced by the LUCAS survey, if national data are not available, and to relate with the new monitoring system set up by the Soil Monitoring Law and the CAP monitoring system.
- SOC dynamics should be estimated by modelling, when properly demonstrated in the scientific literature and calibrated.
- Defines a minimum maintenance time for each eligible CF practice and incentivizes longer projects.
- Sets-up a buffer pool to account for the risk of reversal.
- Applies default-value discount to account for leakage risk, if a reduction in yields is observed.

These recommendations are designed to ensure a harmonized combination of environmental conservation, technical and administrative feasibility, and economic viability for farmers.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Irene Criscuoli: Conceptualization; formal analysis; investigation; methodology; visualization; writing – original draft; writing – review and editing. **Andrea Martelli:** Formal analysis; investigation; methodology; visualization; writing – original draft; writing – review and editing. **Ilaria Falconi:** Investigation; writing – original draft; writing – review and editing. **Francesco Galioto:** Investigation; writing – review and editing. **Maria Valentina Lasorella:** Investigation; writing – review and editing. **Stefania Maurino:** Investigation. **Avion Phillips:** Writing – review and editing. **Guido Bonati:** Conceptualization; funding acquisition; project administration; resources. **Giovanni Dara Guccione:** Conceptualization; investigation; methodology; project administration; resources; supervision; writing – original draft; writing – review and editing.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that supports the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article.

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